

Editorial: How We Addressed the Main Unmet Need in the Medical Literature

The Editors of the Journal of Secondary Endpoints

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Abstract

Have you ever written a manuscript that was too specialist to be funny, yet too ironic, silly, or otherwise implausible to be taken seriously? Had a paper rejected by the *BMJ Christmas Issue*? At that point, the work falls into an editorial no man's land: it either remains in a drawer or is quietly uploaded to Zenodo.

The *Journal of Secondary Endpoints* (JSE) was created precisely to fill this gap, which has been keenly felt by its present Editor-in-Chief.

The idea for JSE did not arrive in a single flash. It emerged gradually. It is the product of a founder-editor who, after accumulating a respectable number of desk rejections over time, reached the only scientifically consistent conclusion: to see certain kinds of work in print, one would have to create a journal tailored to them.

The official narrative is, of course, that "the others" are wrong; that there is a substantial unmet need in the medical literature for material that is currently considered unpublishable.

The story can also be told in more operational terms. It began with a recurring suggestion from a large language model which, in response to almost any questionable idea, would recommend: "You should write this up for the *BMJ Christmas Issue*." On one occasion, that advice was followed. The manuscript was ultimately rejected — but only after a month and a half.

In parallel, the same artificial adviser suggested submitting a different piece to the *Annals of Improbable Research* (AIR). Twenty-nine minutes after submission, the editor's message was crystal clear:

"Most readers do not have sufficient background to appreciate it."

At that point it became evident that there is no stable home for medical satire aimed at a specialist readership. At best, there is a seasonal, hyper-competitive (unlike JSE) Christmas slot, and very little in between.

Thus JSE was founded in response to a systemic unmet need: a space for plausibility-driven, peer-reviewed satire, aimed at clinicians and researchers who occasionally take humour as seriously as they take their secondary endpoints.

JSE's ambition is modest. It does not seek to compete with the *BMJ Christmas Issue* or with AIR, but to complement them, occupying that narrow interstitial space between parody and protocol, between clinical rigour and conceptual nonsense.

The founding of JSE also pays homage to the rejection letter that helped crystallise the idea. In its precision and kindness, it represents a particularly pure form of peer review: the kind that states “this does not fit anywhere”, thereby demonstrating the need to create somewhere new.

Conclusion

Paraphrasing Bender: *“Yeah, well, I’m gonna go build my own journal. With peer review and academic rigor. In fact, forget the journal.”*

If necessity is the mother of invention, rejection is, in this case, its attending physician.

Conflicts of Interest

The Editors declare no conflicts of interest, real or imagined.

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